

GAD

Game creation in augmented reality enhancing professional digital skills

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan

Erasmus + Project

2021-1-IT01-KA210-VET-000034522

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	- 5 -
2. IMPLEMENTATION APPROACHES.....	- 5 -
2.1. TPACK MODEL.....	- 5 -
2.2. DIGCOMP EDU.....	- 7 -
2.3. GAMIFICATION.....	- 10 -
3. REQUIREMENTS FOR HOMOGENEOUS IMPLEMENTATION.....	- 12 -
3.1. The GAD experience.....	- 12 -
3.2. The GAD Game.....	- 12 -
4. MONITORING STRATEGIES AND TOOLS.....	- 13 -
E1.1. USE OF GAD GAME.....	- 13 -
E1.2. QUALITY OF GAD GAME.....	- 14 -
E1.3. QUALITY OF TEACHING EXPERIENCE.....	- 15 -
E1.4. QUALITY OF LEARNING EXPERIENCE.....	- 16 -
E2 PROMOTION AND SHARING OF RESULTS.....	- 17 -
E2.1. COMMUNICATION.....	- 17 -
E2.2. DISSEMINATION.....	- 18 -
E2.3. NETWORKING.....	- 19 -
E3. MONITORING.....	- 20 -
5. MONITORING TOOLS.....	- 21 -
MT-E1.2.A QUESTIONNAIRE QUALITY OF GAD GAME.....	- 21 -
MT-E1.3.A QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS: BASELINE OF DIGITAL SKILLS.....	- 22 -
MT-E1.3.B QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS THROUGH GAD GAME.....	- 24 -
MT-E1.3.C INTERVIEW FOR TEACHERS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS THROUGH GAD GAME.....	- 26 -
MT-E1.4.A QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS: BASELINE OF DIGITAL SKILLS.....	- 27 -
MT-E1.4.B QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF LEARNING THROUGH GAD GAME.....	- 28 -
MT-E1.3.C INTERVIEW FOR STUDENTS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF LEARNING THROUGH GAD GAME.....	- 30 -
MT-E2.1B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF COMMUNICATION.....	- 31 -
MT-E2.2B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF DISSEMINATION.....	- 32 -
MT-E2.3B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF NETWORKING.....	- 33 -
MT-E3.4 QUESTIONNAIRE OS STATUS OF COORDINATION MEASURES.....	- 34 -

1. INTRODUCTION

The present document sets the Monitoring and Evaluation Plan of the Erasmus+ Project GAD Game: Game creation in augmented reality enhancing professional digital skills (2021-1-IT01-KA210-VET-000034522). It consists in an introduction of the implementation approaches of the project (e.g., TPACK model, DIGCOMPEDU, Gamification and Augmented reality), and a set of directives and tools to monitor and assess the quality of the implementation. Those tools are mainly questionnaires and interviews for both trainers and learners. In addition, other tools to monitor both the welfare of the coordination measures, and the communication, dissemination and networking actions, is taken into account.

2. IMPLEMENTATION APPROACHES

2.1. TPACK MODEL

The GAD project is stemmed on the development of integral training competences, based on the technological root of the TPACK model, defined as understanding the connections and interactions between and among content knowledge (subject-matter that is to be taught), technological knowledge (computers, the Internet, digital video, etc.), and pedagogical knowledge (practices, processes, strategies, procedures and methods of teaching and learning) to improve student learning. This model was designed by Mishra and Koehler¹ and distinguishes three basic dimensions of training and four intersections between them, as shown in Figure 1 hereby².

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the TPACK model

¹ Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers college record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.

² Archambault, L. M., & Barnett, J. H. (2010). Revisiting technological pedagogical content knowledge: Exploring the TPACK framework. *Computers & Education*, 55(4), 1656-1662.

The **TPACK model identifies seven dimensions**, along with the differentiated context of training³:

- **Content Knowledge (CK):** it refers to the content knowledge that the teacher possesses in specific matters or areas that must be taught to the students, including concepts, theories, facts and procedures in the area.
- **Pedagogical Knowledge (PK):** it refers to the knowledge possessed by the teacher regarding pedagogical activities, processes, practices, teaching and learning methods used in the teaching-learning process, and how they relate to the educational goals. PK also includes the knowledge of techniques and methods that can be used in the classroom, and strategies to evaluate students.
- **Technological Knowledge (TK):** it refers to the teacher's knowledge regarding different technologies in order to develop the teaching practice. It includes, for instance, knowledge of operating systems and hardware, how to install programs, and how to create documents. It is also important to learn and to adapt to upcoming new technologies.
- **Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK):** it refers to the didactic knowledge about a content area, which implies facilitating the student's learning in that area. This dimension also implies knowing what teaching approaches and strategies are better adapted to the content and how the different elements of content can be worked out for effective teaching.
- **Technological Content Knowledge (TCK):** this includes the knowledge of how to represent specific concepts with technology, which means the way technology and discipline are reciprocally linked. Teachers need to know the way the contents in their respective areas are being affected by the application of technologies.
- **Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK):** refers to the knowledge of general pedagogical strategies that can be performed thanks to technology. This includes knowing the appropriate tools for a specific task, the abilities to choose the right tool based on the efficiency or adequacy to the task, and the ability to apply pedagogical strategies when using technologies.
- **Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK):** refers to a teacher's knowledge on how to develop specific didactic strategies on different matters using ICT in order to facilitate learning. Therefore, it is a form of knowledge that goes beyond these three components (content, pedagogy, and technology). TPACK includes, for example, the knowledge of pedagogical strategies that allow the effective use of technologies to teach the content of the discipline, and the knowledge of the aspects that make the content easy or difficult to learn, and how technology can help with some of the problems that students face.

The TPACK is a framework for teacher knowledge, and as such, it may be helpful to those planning professional development for teachers by illuminating what teachers need to know about technology, pedagogy, and content and their interrelationships. However, as

³ Rodríguez Moreno, J., Agreda Montoro, M., & Ortiz Colón, A. (2019). Changes in Teacher Training within the TPACK Model Framework: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 11(7), 1870. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su11071870>

many studies reveal⁴⁻⁵, the TPACK framework does not specify how this should be accomplished, recognizing that there are many possible approaches to knowledge development of this type. The GAD project will approach the pedagogical and technological knowledges, based on the development of augmented reality experiences. It will focus on specific digital education competences, as defined by the DigComEdu, as explained as follows.

2.2. DIGCOMP EDU

The GAD project stems from the need to qualify the digital skills (**DiGCompEDU**) of trainers (teachers, educators, etc.) highlighted by recent European studies. Many European States are about to or have already developed self-assessment tools and programmes to qualify education and the professional development of trainers⁶.

In **lifelong learning and vocational training paths** it is crucial to use tailored methodologies to engage young students and adults, to customise the training courses, to make the contents appealing to the target groups, focusing on the different channels through which people learn and communicate (orality, neo-orality, press)⁷. Each of these aspects represents an essential variable that trainers should take into account to reach educational and learning objectives.

Trainers' competent use of digital technologies leads to the creation of innovative and engaging educational opportunities for young and adult learners, while promoting a productive and creative participation in digital society and increasing the level of inclusion in learning paths⁸.

The GAD project combines the need to improve and enhance trainers' digital teaching methods and tools with **the need to motivate students to learn**.

"Being able to identify learners' professional and individual development needs" and the *proficiency to motivate and learn* enhance trainers' *ability to deliver information and, at the same time, share with students the willingness to know and learn to "do"*. The ongoing development and upgrading of professional skills is a mandatory requirement for trainers so that they can identify efficient and innovative educational strategies.

GAD aims to strengthen the following digital skills of trainers (educators/teachers):

⁴ Harris, J., Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. (2009). Teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge and learning activity types: Curriculum-based technology integration reframed. *Journal of research on technology in education*, 41(4), 393-416.

⁵ Cox, S., & Graham, C. R. (2009). Using an elaborated model of the TPACK framework to analyze and depict teacher knowledge. *TechTrends*, 53(5), 60-69.

⁶ TALIS-2018

⁷ W. J. Ong, *Oralità e scrittura*.

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/european-framework-digital-competence-educators-digcompedu>

Developing, integrating, and re-elaborating digital content (6.3, 2.2), Developing digital effective learning modes (3.3, 3.4, 6.2), Actively involving students (5.3), Using digital technologies in a responsible way (6.4), Solving problems (6.5).

The DigCompEdu Framework synthesizes national and regional efforts to capture educator-specific digital competences. It is directed towards educators at all levels of education, from early childhood to higher and adult education, including general and vocational training, special needs education, and non-formal learning contexts. The framework is based on work carried out by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), on behalf of the Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC).

Teachers and educators are role models for the next generation. It is therefore vital for them to be equipped with the digital competence all citizens need to be able to actively participate in a digital society. The European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) specifies these competences. DigComp has become a widely accepted tool for measuring and certifying Digital Competence and has been used as a basis for teacher training and professional development across and beyond Europe. As citizens, educators need to be equipped with these competences to participate in society, both personally and professionally. As role models, they need to be able to clearly demonstrate their digital competence to learners and to pass on their creative and critical use of digital technologies. However, teachers and educators are not just role models. They are first and foremost learning facilitators, or more plainly: teachers. As professionals dedicated to teaching, they need, in addition to the general digital competences for life and work, educator-specific digital competences to be able to effectively use digital technologies for teaching.

Figure 2. Scheme of DigComEdu Framework. Source: Joint Research Council

The DigCompEdu Framework aims to capture and describe the **educator-specific digital competences organised in 6 areas:**

- **Area 1** is directed at the broader professional environment, i.e. educators' use of digital technologies in professional interactions with colleagues, learners, parents

and other interested parties, for their own individual professional development and for the collective good of the organisation.

- **Area 2** looks at the competences needed to effectively and responsibly use, create and share digital resources for learning.
- **Area 3** is dedicated to managing and orchestrating the use of digital technologies in teaching and learning.
- **Area 4** addresses the use of digital strategies to enhance assessment.
- **Area 5** focuses on the potential of digital technologies for learner-centred teaching and learning strategies.
- **Area 6** details the specific pedagogic competences required to facilitate students' digital competence.

In the GAD project specifically, the following areas will be developed, through the enhancement of the selected skills:

2/ Digital Resources

Creating and modifying digital resources: to modify and build on existing openly-licensed resources and other resources where this is permitted; to create or co-create new digital educational resources; to consider the specific learning objective, context, pedagogical approach, and learner group, when designing digital resources and planning their use.

3/ Teaching and Learning

Guidance: to use digital technologies and services to enhance the interaction with learners, individually and collectively, within and outside the learning session. To use digital technologies to offer timely and targeted guidance and assistance; to experiment with and develop new forms and formats for offering guidance and support.

Collaborative learning: to use digital technologies; to foster and enhance learner collaboration; to enable learners to use digital technologies as part of collaborative assignments, as a means of enhancing communication, collaboration and collaborative knowledge creation.

5/ Empowering Learners

To provide equitable access to appropriate digital technologies and resources, e.g. ensuring that all students have access to the digital technologies used.

Actively engaging learners: to use digital technologies to foster learners' active and creative engagement with a subject matter; to use digital technologies within pedagogic strategies that foster learners' transversal skills, deep thinking and creative expression; to open up learning to new, real-world contexts, which involve learners themselves in hands-on activities, scientific investigation or complex problem solving, or in other ways increase learners' active involvement in complex subject matters

6/ Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence

Digital communication and collaboration: to incorporate learning activities, assignments and assessments which require learners to effectively and responsibly use digital technologies for communication, collaboration and civic participation;

Responsible use: to take measures to ensure learners' physical, psychological and social wellbeing while using digital technologies. To empower learners to manage risks and use digital technologies safely and responsibly.

Digital problem solving: to incorporate learning activities, assignments and assessments which require learners to identify and solve technical problems, or to transfer technological knowledge creatively to new situations.

2.3. GAMIFICATION

Gamification is nowadays a methodological approach that is essential to improve the **attention, participation, and motivation of students at all levels**. According to Kapp⁹, gamification is “using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve problems.” In education, gamification is a technique that proposes dynamics associated with game design in the educational environment, in order to stimulate and have direct interaction with students, allowing them to significantly develop their curricular, cognitive, and social competences. It is the use of techniques to engage people, motivate their action, and promote learning and problem solving. This generates in the students a feeling of empowerment in their way of working to achieve tasks, making them more attractive and promoting cooperative work, effort, and other positive values typical of games¹⁰⁻¹¹.

Therefore, gamification is the use of game thinking, approaches and elements in a context different from the games. Using game mechanics improves motivation and learning in formal and informal conditions, and the academic interest has increased worldwide¹². Games have some **distinctive features** which play a key role in gamification, and therefore must be considered when designing a teaching-learning experience:

- **Users**/students are all participants.
- **challenges**/tasks that users perform and progress towards defined objectives.
- **points** that are accumulated because of executing tasks.
- **levels** which users pass depending on the points.

⁹ Kapp, K. M. (2012). The gamification of learning and instruction: game-based methods and strategies for training and education. John Wiley & Sons.

¹⁰ Trigueros, R., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Lopez-Liria, R., Cangas, A. J., González, J. J., & Álvarez, J. F. (2020). The role of perception of support in the classroom on the students' motivation and emotions: the impact on metacognition strategies and academic performance in math and english classes. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2794.

¹¹ Alsawaier, R. S. (2018). The effect of gamification on motivation and engagement. *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*.

¹² Swacha, J. (2021). State of Research on Gamification in Education: A Bibliometric Survey. *Education Sciences*, 11(2), 69. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/educsci11020069>

- **badges** which serve as rewards for completing actions.
- **ranking** of users according to their achievements.

The use of gamification can be beneficial at different educational levels, from school to university. Some studies reveal that the main gamification elements used in education are usually points, medals, rankings, and narrative. However, it is valued that when only one or two gamified elements are used, such as points or badges, the effects on student motivation are less or may even be negative¹³. It is, therefore, essential to design a complete learning experience, taking into account the profile(s) of the final user(s).

The use of **gamification pedagogical strategies** to enhance the concept of Education 4.0 in the classroom is a cornerstone of future teaching-learning experiences. Education 4.0 builds on the concept of learning by doing, in which students are encouraged to learn and discover different things in singular ways based on experimentation. A residual adoption of serious games and gamification approaches still only appear in less than 20% of projects, according to a recent study¹⁴, which therefore represents a niche for innovation and development. Despite this low penetration rate, the potential of using serious games and industry 4.0 tools is recognized as a practice to broaden, transform and innovate the curriculum, teaching practices and learning. However, it is also recognized that the use of these tools requires a change of roles, attitudes and beliefs about the learning of both students and teachers. Some challenges and difficulties in its adoption, namely the simplification that most of these tools make of the real world, the difficulties of its integration in the didactical system and the limitations of the system in responding to non-predefined stimuli from the external environment, have to be also tackled. Augmented reality in education, which will be focused in the following section, is a particular methodological approach that can be used for gamifying the classroom and boost motivation and skills development of students^{15, 16}.

¹³ Manzano-León, A., Camacho-Lazarraga, P., Guerrero, M. A., Guerrero-Puerta, L., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Trigueros, R., & Alias, A. (2021). Between Level Up and Game Over: A Systematic Literature Review of Gamification in Education. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 2247. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13042247>

¹⁴ Almeida, F., & Simoes, J. (2019). The role of serious games, gamification and industry 4.0 tools in the education 4.0 paradigm. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 10(2), 120-136.

¹⁵ Chauhan, J., Taneja, S., & Goel, A. (2015, October). Enhancing MOOC with augmented reality, adaptive learning and gamification. In 2015 IEEE 3rd International Conference on MOOCs, Innovation and Technology in Education (MITE) (pp. 348-353). IEEE.

¹⁶ Colpani, R., & Homem, M. R. P. (2015, July). An innovative augmented reality educational framework with gamification to assist the learning process of children with intellectual disabilities. In 2015 6th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications (IISA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR HOMOGENEOUS IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. The GAD experience

In order to cover a comparable result, the **framework of the application of the GAD experience has to be similar in all places**. Therefore, a schematic methodological approach is shown as follows:

1. Create GAD teams (5/6 people each).
2. Set up the minimum criteria/settings of the expected GAD game for each team.
 - Questionnaire-baseline-teacher
3. Creation of GAD Game, based on a training/tutoring program.
4. Involve Trainers in Project launch event.
5. Presentation of GAD Game to students
 - Questionnaire-baseline-students
6. Performance of, at least, 2 lessons + 2 content-related quizzes (4 GAD interactions) with the GAD Game
 - Questionnaire-improvement teaching – Teachers
 - Interview-improvement teaching – Teachers
 - Questionnaire-improvement learning-Students
 - Interview-improvement learning-Students
7. Complete showcase template
8. Involve Trainers and Students in engagement and dissemination events

3.2. The GAD Game

The GAD game should consider the following issues:

- Duration: students should be able to play it in 10-15 min.
- Amount of contents: 5-7 descriptors per GAD game.
- Interaction of contents: at least,
 - 1 with text annotations.
- Quizzes: 3-5 questions, both multiple choice, or true/false.

4. MONITORING STRATEGIES AND TOOLS

E1.1. USE OF GAD GAME

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the adoption and transferability potential of the GAD Game
Uses	Provision of data for management control
Foci	Networking events Round Tables Communication events (social networks)
Data and evidence	Number of App downloads Number of GAD uses TOOL: KPI table
Audience	Teachers, Tutors, Trainers, Educational leaders
Timing	Months 10-14-16
Agency	Transfer agents.

KPI TARGETS

E1.1.A. Number of App downloads: 250 (M16), 300 (F+6)

E1.1.B. Number of GAD uses (webpage monitoring): 30 (M16), 50 (F+6)

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E1.1 Monitoring Table for Use of GAD Game

E1.2. QUALITY OF GAD GAME

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the advantages of GAD Game by itself and through benchmarking with other tools
Uses	Increase usability and transferability of the GAD Game. Improve the after-GAD project
Foci	Design, Production and Testing of GAD Game
Data and evidence	Degree of satisfaction TOOL: Questionnaire (Z/Country/Mi)
Audience	Designers
Timing	Months 10-14
Agency	GAD Steering Committee + Tool Testers

KPI TARGETS

E1.2.A. Number of questionnaires received (12, M16)

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E1.2.A Questionnaire Quality GAD Game

E1.3. QUALITY OF TEACHING EXPERIENCE

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Teaching experience of using GAD
Uses	Help in the design of GAD Game and complementary Training needs for Teachers-Trainers-Tutors
Foci	Testing of GAD Game
Data and evidence	Degree of satisfaction Degree of willingness of application Degree of digital literacy improvement Detection of needs of training TOOL: Questionnaire-baseline (M7) TOOL: Questionnaire-GAD application (M11) TOOL: Interview (M14)
Audience	Teachers-Trainers-Tutors
Timing	Months 7-10-14
Agency	Trainers coordinators

KPI TARGETS

E1.3.A. Number of Baseline Questionnaires = 5/ country

E1.3.B. Number of after-GAD Questionnaires = 5/ country

E1.3.C. Number of after-GAD Interviews = 5/ country

E1.3.D. %Perception of increase of digital skills of teachers (Likert 3.5-5) = 75%

E1.3.E. %Perception of willingness to use VR and GAD among teachers (Likert 3.5-5) = 75%

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E1.3.A. Questionnaire for Teachers: Baseline Perception of Digital skills

MT-E1.3.B. Questionnaire for Teachers: Perception of Improvement of Digital skills through GAD Game

MT-E1.3.C. Interview for Teachers: Perception of Improvement of Digital skills through GAD Game

E1.4. QUALITY OF LEARNING EXPERIENCE

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Learning experience of using GAD
Uses	Help in the design of GAD Game and complementary Training needs for Teachers-Trainers-Tutors
Foci	Testing of GAD Game
Data and evidence	Degree of satisfaction Degree of willingness of application TOOL: Questionnaire-baseline (M7) TOOL: Questionnaire-GAD application (M11) TOOL: Interview (M14)
Audience	Students (School, VET, UNIV)
Timing	Months 10-14
Agency	Teachers/Tutors/Trainers through Trainers coordinators

KPI TARGETS

E1.4.A. Number of Baseline Questionnaires = 50 students/country

E1.4.B. Number of after-GAD Questionnaires = 50 students/country

E1.4.C. Number of after-GAD Interviews = 10 students/country

E1.4.D. %Perception of involvement in teaching through VR and GAD (Likert 3.5-5) = 75%

E1.4.E. %Perception of willingness to use VR and GAD for learning (Likert 3.5-5) = 75%

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E1.4.A. Questionnaire for Students: Baseline Perception of Digital skills

MT-E1.4.B. Questionnaire for Students: Perception of Improvement of Learning through GAD Game

MT-E1.4.C. Interview for Teachers: Perception of Improvement of Learning through GAD Game

E2 PROMOTION AND SHARING OF RESULTS

E2.1. COMMUNICATION

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Quality and Reach of Communication activities
Uses	Monitoring the effectiveness of the communication strategy
Foci	Narrative, adapted message and useful means
Data and evidence	Meeting checks Visual identity GAD web and social networks TOOL: KPI Table TOOL: Questionnaire of Communication Review
Audience	GAD Steering Committee
Timing	Months 6-10-14-16
Agency	GAD Steering Committee

KPI TARGETS

- E2.1.A. Int. Com - Online Meetings (M2-6-10-14): 4
- E2.1.B. Int. Com - Shared folder checks (M2-6-10-14): 4
- E2.1.C. Int. Com - Agreed Logo (M3):1
- E2.1.D. Visual identity toolkit (doc,pwp,poster,roll-up...) (M3): 1
- E2.1.E. GAD Webpage – visitors: 250
- E2.1.F. GAD Mailing list-suscribers: 100
- E2.1.G. GAD FB posts: 50
- E2.1.H. GAD Instagram posts:50
- E2.1.I. GAD Webpage – visitors: 50
- E2.1.J. GAD Web banner: 1
- E2.1.K. GAD Communication - Revision of strategy (M2-6-10-14): 4

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

- MT-E2.1.A Monitoring Table for Communication
- MT-E2.1.B Questionnaire for Communication Review

E2.2. DISSEMINATION

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Quality and Reach of Dissemination activities
Uses	Monitoring the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy
Foci	Narrative, adapted message and useful means
Data and evidence	Meeting checks Visual identity GAD-related elaborated documents TOOL: KPI Table TOOL: Questionnaire of Dissemination Review
Audience	GAD Steering Committee
Timing	Months 6-10-14
Agency	GAD Steering Committee

KPI TARGETS

E2.2.A. GAD Brochures-3 languages: 100

E2.2.B. GAD Newsletter: 5

E2.2.C. GAD site in Erasmus+ Project Results Platform + Zenodo: 1

E2.2.D. GAD sites in Partner's webs: 3

E2.2.E. GAD mentions in Educational apps portals: 3

E2.2.F. GAD Documents/articles (10 launch + 10 dissemination phase): 20

E2.2.G. GAD Dissemination - Revision of strategy (M2-6-10-14): 4

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E2.2.A Monitoring Table for Dissemination

MT-E2.2.B Questionnaire for Dissemination Review

E2.3. NETWORKING

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Quality and Reach of Networking activities
Uses	Monitoring the effectiveness of the networking strategy
Foci	Round tables, networking events and engagement of new users
Data and evidence	Networking events Dissemination of networking events Engagement of users TOOL: KPI Table TOOL: Questionnaire of Networking Review
Audience	GAD Steering Committee
Timing	Months 6-10-14-16
Agency	GAD Steering Committee

KPI TARGETS

E2.3.A. GAD Project launch (1/ country): 3

E2.3.B. GAD Project launch - Press release: 1

E2.3.C. GAD Round Table (2): 2

E2.3.D. GAD Round Table - Video reports (5): 5

E2.3.E. GAD Dissemination events - Participation (3/ country): 9

E2.3.F. GAD Dissemination events - (1 / event): 9

E2.3.G. Participants in GAD events: 15 teachers + 30 policy makers, experts, local stakeholders)

E2.3.H. Participants in GAD project – Teachers: 20

E2.3.I. Participants in GAD project – Students: 150

E2.3.J. GAD Networking - Revision of strategy (M2-6-10-14): 4

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E2.3.A Monitoring Table for Networking

MT-E2.3.B Questionnaire for Networking Review

E3. MONITORING

RUFDATA APPROACH

Reasons and purposes	Measure the Quality of project activities
Uses	Improving the effectiveness of the project
Foci	Monitoring meetings
Data and evidence	Monitoring meetings Accomplishment of expected results and timetable Engagement of consortium members TOOL: KPI Table TOOL: Questionnaire of Management satisfaction
Audience	GAD Steering Committee
Timing	Months 7-11-15+F
Agency	GAD Steering Committee

KPI TARGETS

E3.1. Accomplishment of timetable, milestones, resources and results and coordination

E3.1.a. Report of technical monitoring (m7-11-15-f): 4

E3.2. Budget and expenditures of financial resources

E3.2.a. Report of financial monitoring (m7-11-15-f):4

E3.3. Deliverables and technical reports

E3.3.a gad game

E3.4. Welfare of coordination

E3.4.a. Report of coordination issues (m7-11-15-f):4

E3.4.b. Satisfaction above 3,5/5 in 75% of participants

KPI-MONITORING TOOL

MT-E3.A Monitoring Table for Monitoring

MT-E3.B Questionnaire for Status of coordination measures

5. MONITORING TOOLS

MT-E1.2.A QUESTIONNAIRE QUALITY OF GAD GAME

PROCEDURE

A. Choose 2 already existing AR tools for learning and benchmark them with the GAD Game. For this, the recommendation is to simulate a lesson slot, by following the steps: creation/selection-application/testing.

B. Answer the following questions

C. Send this questionnaire to your contact person.

1. Identify the chosen AR Tools
2. Explain the type of use that has been tested.
3. Complete the following ranking table (1-poor to 5-excellent)

Features	Tool 1	Tool 2	GAD Game
Usability			
Versatility			
Accessibility			
Attractiveness			

4. Point out 3 main features of GAD Game
 - Feature 1:
 - Feature 2:
 - Feature 3:
5. Point out 3 main advantages of GAD Game
 - Advantage 1:
 - Advantage 2:
 - Advantage 3:
6. Please include recommendations to help introduce the GAD Game in the training process

MT-E1.3.A QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS: BASELINE OF DIGITAL SKILLS

PROCEDURE

- A. Attend to the on-line / face-to-face presentation of the GAD project
- B. Answer the following questions, with the support of partners of the GAD Game.
- C. Send this on-line questionnaire to the person of contact.

SECTION 1. Digital literacy skills

1. Rate perception for developing, integrating and re-elaborating digital content (Likert scale 1-5)
2. Rate perception for digital effective learning modes (Likert scale 1-5)
3. Rate perception for actively involving students through digital means (Likert scale 1-5)
4. Rate perception for using digital technologies in a responsible way (Likert scale 1-5)
5. Rate perception for solving problems by digital means (Likert scale 1-5)
6. Rate knowledge of the DigCompEdu (Likert scale 1-5)
7. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 2. Use of augmented reality

8. Rate of experience in augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
9. Name digital tools most commonly used for augmented reality (Free space)
10. Perception of difficulty of using augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
11. Rate of interest in augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
12. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 3. Knowledge of TPACK model, Life-long learning and innovation

13. Awareness of TPACK model for trainers (Likert scale 1-5)
14. Rate perception of level at the knowledge dimension (Likert scale 1-5)
15. Rate perception of level at the pedagogical dimension (Likert scale 1-5)
16. Rate perception of level at the digital dimension (Likert scale 1-5)
17. Rate perception of level as teacher, in general (Likert scale 1-5)
18. Rate of interest in upskilling/reskilling training skills (Likert scale 1-5)
19. Hours of extra-training during the last 3 years (Number required)
20. Rate of interest in innovative education (Likert scale 1-5)
21. Number of projects of educative innovation in which the teacher has been involved in the last 3 years (Number required)
22. Rate perception of level of gamification for training (Likert scale 1-5)
23. Rate of willingness of getting involved in innovative educational projects concerning augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
24. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 4. Teaching context

25. Country

- 26. City
- 27. Type of training centre: primary/secondary/VET/university/adults/other (specify)
- 28. Level of training
- 29. Subject/Area of teaching
- 30. Number of students/classroom (Average Number required)
- 31. Adequacy of digital tools in the training centre (Likert scale)
- 32. Adequacy of digital tools of the students (Likert scale)
- 33. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 5. Personal context

- 34. Age (Number required)
- 35. Gender (Male / Female / Non-binary)
- 36. Years as trainer (Number required)
- 37. Other relevant comments (free space)

MT-E1.3.B QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS THROUGH GAD GAME

PROCEDURE

- A. Apply GAD game in 2 lessons + 2 quizzes, and compare to a previous teaching scenario
- B. Answer the following questions
- C. Send this questionnaire to your contact person

SECTION 1. Digital literacy skills

1. Rate perception of improvement for developing, integrating and re-elaborating digital content (Likert scale 1-5)
2. Rate perception of improvement for digital effective learning modes (Likert scale 1-5)
3. Rate perception of improvement for actively involving students through digital means (Likert scale 1-5)
4. Rate perception of improvement for using digital technologies in a responsible way (Likert scale 1-5)
5. Rate perception of improvement for solving problems by digital means (Likert scale 1-5)
6. Rate improvement of knowledge of the DigCompEdu (Likert scale 1-5)
7. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 2. Use of augmented reality

8. Rate of improvement of experience in augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
9. Name other digital tools tested for augmented reality (Free space)
10. Perception of difficulty of using augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
11. Rate of interest in augmented reality for teaching (Likert scale 1-5)
12. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 3. Use of GAD Game

13. Rate Usability of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
14. Rate Versatility of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
15. Rate Accessibility of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
16. Rate Attractiveness of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
17. Rate perception of impact of augmented reality for teaching content (Likert scale 1-5)
18. Rate perception of impact of augmented reality for assessment activities (Likert scale 1-5)
19. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 4. Use of GAD Game

20. Rate perception of improvement of teaching-learning process by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)

21. Rate perception of improvement of attention of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
22. Rate perception of improvement of participation of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
23. Rate perception of improvement of motivation of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
24. Rate perception of improvement of understanding of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
25. Rate perception of improvement of marks of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
26. Rate of willingness to continue using the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
27. Rate of willingness to recommend the use of the GAD Game to other colleagues (Likert scale 1-5)
28. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 3. Knowledge of TPACK model, Life-long learning and innovation

29. Rate improvement perception of level at the knowledge dimension of the TPACK model (Likert scale 1-5)
30. Rate improvement perception of level at the pedagogical dimension of the TPACK model (Likert scale 1-5)
31. Rate improvement perception of level at the digital dimension of the TPACK model (Likert scale 1-5)
32. Rate improvement perception of level as teacher, in general (Likert scale 1-5)
33. Rate improvement of interest in upskilling/reskilling training skills (Likert scale 1-5)
34. Rate of improvement of willingness of getting involved in innovative educational projects concerning augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
35. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 4. Teaching context

36. Country
37. City
38. Type of training centre: primary/secondary/VET/university/adults/other (specify)
39. Level of training
40. Subject/Area of teaching
41. Number of students/classroom (Average Number required)
42. Adequacy of digital tools in the training centre (Likert scale)
43. Adequacy of digital tools of the students (Likert scale)
44. Type of activity (Free space)
45. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 5. Personal context

46. Age (Number required)
47. Gender (Male/Female/Non-binary)
48. Years as trainer (Number required)
49. Other relevant comments (free space)

MT-E1.3.C INTERVIEW FOR TEACHERS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF DIGITAL SKILLS THROUGH GAD GAME

PROCEDURE

- A. Make sure the teachers have applied GAD game and can compare to a previous teaching scenario and that have answered completely previous questionnaire MT-E1.3.B. Make a face-to-face meeting with the teacher, around a coffee.
- B. Take note of the answers to the following questions.
- C. Send this interview to your contact person.

QUESTIONS

1. Have you heard about the T-PACK model and the DigComEdu before the participation in this project? What are your strengths and features to improve, in terms of digital skills?

2. Have you used before augmented reality during training? How was the experience with the GAD Game?

3. What type of innovation did you introduce in your training program with GAD? How did it work?

4. Point out 3 key features of the GAD Game, and 3 features to improve.

5. Which upskilling/reskilling needs have you detected and how would you address them? How could the GAD team help?

6. Please feel free to leave any comment

MT-E1.4.A QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS: BASELINE OF DIGITAL SKILLS

PROCEDURE

- A. Attend to a presentation of the GAD Game and a showcase by the teacher (not the students).
- B. Answer the following questions.
- C. Send this questionnaire to your contact person.

SECTION 1. Use of augmented reality

1. Rate of experience in augmented reality for learning, at classroom (Likert scale 1-5)
2. Rate of experience in augmented reality for learning, at home (Likert scale 1-5)
3. Rate of experience in augmented reality for playing, at home (Likert scale 1-5)
4. Name digital tools most commonly used for augmented reality (Free space)
5. Rate of interest in augmented reality for learning (Likert scale 1-5)
6. Perception of difficulty of using augmented reality for learning due to own restrictions (Likert scale 1-5)
7. Perception of difficulty of using augmented reality for learning due to teacher restrictions (Likert scale 1-5)
8. Perception of difficulty of using augmented reality for learning due to school restrictions (Likert scale 1-5)
9. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 2. Learning modes

10. Rate of satisfaction with traditional teaching modes (Likert scale 1-5)
11. Rate of satisfaction with innovative teaching modes (Likert scale 1-5)
12. Rate of experience in using digital tools for learning, at classroom (Likert scale 1-5)
13. Rate of experience in using digital tools for learning, at home (Likert scale 1-5)
14. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 3. Learning context

15. Country
16. City
17. Type of training centre: primary/secondary/VET/university/adults/other (specify)
18. Level of training
19. Subject/Area of teaching
20. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 4. Personal context

21. Age (Number required)
22. Gender (Male/Female/Non-binary)
23. Other relevant comments (free space)

MT-E1.4.B QUESTIONNAIRE FOR STUDENTS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF LEARNING THROUGH GAD GAME

PROCEDURE

- A. Attend to 2 lessons + 2 quizzes in which GAD Game is used.
- B. Answer the following questions.
- C. Send this questionnaire to your contact person.

SECTION 1. Use of GAD Game

1. Rate Usability of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
2. Rate Versatility of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
3. Rate Accessibility of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
4. Rate Attractiveness of the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
5. Rate perception of impact of augmented reality for learning content (Likert scale 1-5)
6. Rate perception of impact of augmented reality for assessment activities (Likert scale 1-5)
7. Rate perception of improvement of attention of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
8. Rate perception of improvement of participation of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
9. Rate perception of improvement of motivation of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
10. Rate perception of improvement of understanding of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
11. Rate perception of improvement of marks of students by the use of augmented reality (Likert scale 1-5)
12. Rate of willingness to continue using the GAD Game (Likert scale 1-5)
13. Rate of willingness to recommend the use of the GAD Game in other subjects (Likert scale 1-5)
14. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 2. Learning context

15. Country
16. City
17. Type of training centre: primary/secondary/VET/university/adults/other (specify)
18. Level of training (Free space)
19. Subject/Area of teaching (Free space)
20. Adequacy of digital tools in the training centre (Likert scale)
21. Adequacy of digital tools of the students (Likert scale)
22. Type of activity (Free space)
23. Other relevant comments (Free space)

SECTION 3. Personal context

- 24. Age (Number required)
- 25. Gender (Male / Female / Non-binary)
- 26. Other relevant comments (free space)

MT-E1.3.C INTERVIEW FOR STUDENTS: PERCEPTION OF IMPROVEMENT OF LEARNING THROUGH GAD GAME

PROCEDURE

A. Make sure the students have received lessons through GAD game and can compare to a previous teaching, scenario and that have answered completely previous questionnaire MT-E1.4.B. Make a face-to-face meeting with the students, around a refresh. It could be recommendable to experience a lively interview, so it could be videotaped or audiotaped. Check Image rights.

B. Take note of the answers to the following questions.

C. Send this interview to your contact person.

QUESTIONS

1. Have you used before augmented reality during training? How was the experience with the GAD Game?

2. What type of innovation did you experience in your training program with GAD? How did it work?

3. Point out 3 key features of the GAD Game, and 3 features to improve.

4. Which needs have you detected and how would you address them? How could your teacher help?

5. Please feel free to leave any comment

MT-E2.1B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF COMMUNICATION

PROCEDURE

A. Answer the following questions.

B. Send this questionnaire to the project manager:

1. How would you rate the Communication performance of the consortium? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
2. How would you rate the Communication performance of your entity? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
3. List the communication activities that your entity has performed during this reporting term.
4. Have you encountered difficulties in the implementation of the Communication strategies? How have them been solved ? (Open Question)
5. Do you consider that the communication messages are appropriate in relationship with the current status of the project? Is there any idea that should be revised? Is there any idea that should be strengthened? (Open Question)
6. What is your plan of communication for the next reporting term? (Open Question)

MT-E2.2B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF DISSEMINATION

PROCEDURE

A. Answer the following questions.

B. Send this questionnaire to the project manager:

1. How would you rate the Dissemination performance of the consortium? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
2. How would you rate the Dissemination performance of your entity? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
3. List the dissemination activities that your entity has performed during this reporting term.
4. Have you encountered difficulties in the implementation of the Dissemination strategies? How have them been solved? (Open Question)
5. Do you consider that the dissemination means are appropriate in relationship with the current status of the project? Is there any idea that should be revised? Is there any idea that should be strengthened? (Open Question)
6. What is your plan of dissemination for the next reporting term? (Open Question)

MT-E2.3B. QUESTIONNAIRE OF NETWORKING

PROCEDURE

A. Answer the following questions.

B. Send this questionnaire to the project manager:

1. How would you rate the Networking performance of the consortium? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
2. How would you rate the Networking performance of your entity? (Likert Scale: 1-5)
3. List the networking activities that your entity has performed during this reporting term.
4. Have you encountered difficulties in the implementation of the Networking strategies? How have them been solved? (Open Question)
5. Do you consider that the networking means are appropriate in relationship with the current status of the project? Is there any idea that should be revised? Is there any idea that should be strengthened? (Open Question)
6. What is your plan of networking for the next reporting term? (Open Question)

MT-E3.4 QUESTIONNAIRE ON STATUS OF COORDINATION MEASURES

PROCEDURE

A. Answer the following questions.

B. Send this questionnaire to the project manager:

1. Rate your perception of the welfare of the consortium, in general terms (Likert Scale: 1-5)
2. Rate your perception of the effectiveness of the Technical Development of the GAD Game (Likert Scale: 1-5)
3. Rate your perception of the effectiveness of the Internal Communication Measures of the GAD Game (Likert Scale: 1-5)
4. Rate your perception of the effectiveness of the External Communication and Dissemination Measures of the GAD Game (Likert Scale: 1-5)
5. Rate your perception of the effectiveness of the Monitoring Measures of the GAD Game (Likert Scale: 1-5)
6. Rate your perception of the progress of the GAD Project at national level (Likert Scale: 1-5)
7. Rate your perception of the progress of the GAD Project at international level (Likert Scale: 1-5)
8. Have you encountered difficulties in the implementation of the GAD Game at national level? How have them been solved? (Open Question)
9. Have you encountered difficulties in the Communication and Dissemination at national level? How have them been solved? (Open Question)
10. Have you encountered difficulties in the Management and Monitoring? How have them been solved? (Open Question)

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